

Plant density, dry matter production, N concentration, and N accumulation of *Sesbania rostrata* at different seeding rate IRRI farm, Philippines, 1987 wet season.

Seeding rate (kg/ha)	Dry matter (mg/ha)		Plant density (plants/m ²)	Leaf N (g/kg)	Stem N (g/kg)	Total plant N (kg/ha)
	Leaf	Stem				
20	1.2	2.7	55	46	9	81
30	1.3	3.0	70	46	8	85
40	1.6	4.1	107	47	9	114
50	1.5	3.9	119	46	8	100
LSD (0.05)	0.1	0.3	10	2	1	8

These results suggest that the higher plant densities resulting from seeding rates above 40 kg/ha decrease organic matter production and N accumulation of sesbania plants. A plant density of 100 plants/m² seems to be optimum for maximum N accumulation.

To achieve a plant density of about 100 plants/m², seeding rates may have to be adjusted for soil textures, climates, and field conditions. ■

Physiology and plant nutrition

Effects of a growth regulator on rice seedling growth

J. Ahmed, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, West Bengal, India

Growth regulator Triacantanol has been found effective in increasing biomass production in cereals and vegetable crops.

Triacantanol increases plant height and weight within a few days of application and stimulates nutrient assimilation.

Seeds of semidwarf IET4094 and IR42 and tall indica NC492 rice varieties were soaked 1 h before sowing in 3 concentrations of TRIA (n-Triacantanol): 0.01, 0.10, and 1.00 ppm, with three replications. Root length, root volume,

seedling height, seedling dry weight, and leaf number were recorded 25 d after seeding.

In general, seedlings treated with TRIA were superior to those with no treatment (see table). Late-maturing NC492 and IR42 showed better results than medium-maturing IET4094 in all treatments, for all characters. No toxic, abnormal, or atypical morphological changes were observed at the concentrations used. ■

Effect of n-Triacantanol on rice seedling characters.

n-Triacantanol (mg/liter)	Root length (cm/plant)			Root volume (ml/plant)			Seedling height (cm/plant)			Leaf no. per seedling			Seedling dry wt (mg/plant)		
	IET4094	IR42	NC492	IET4094	IR42	NC492	IET4094	IR42	NC492	IET4094	IR42	NC492	IET4094	IR42	NC492
0.00	21.2	15.3	17.6	0.2	0.1	0.2	27.4	20.2	37.4	4.9	4.1	4.2	114	137	211
0.01	21.8	21.5	19.5	0.3	0.3	0.3	27.7	25.2	38.6	4.9	4.9	4.7	171	219	237
0.10	21.8	18.6	20.4	0.3	0.2	0.5	27.6	24.1	39.5	5.0	4.9	4.4	181	207	253
1.00	21.8	18.6	18.1	0.3	0.3	0.3	27.6	23.9	37.8	5.0	4.9	4.5	186	202	217
CV (%)	7.8			10.1			4.2			2.9			5.8		
LSD (0.05)	2.6			0.1			2.1			0.2			18		

Fertilizer management

Greenhouse evaluation of urea supergranules (USG) containing diammonium phosphate (DAP) for transplanted rice

N. K. Savant and S. H. Chien, International Fertilizer Development Center (IFDC), P.O. Box 2040, Muscle Shoals, Alabama 35662, USA

Serious losses of fertilizer N and P to runoff are common in transplanted rainfed ricefields of small farmers in South and Southeast Asia. Losses occur primarily because farmers are unable to properly incorporate fertilizers into soils with varying depths of nonflowing or

flowing floodwaters. A ready-made, balanced NP fertilizer and an alternative application method are needed.

Phosphatic fertilizers containing Ca(H₂PO₄)₂ · H₂O (such as single or triple superphosphate [TSP]) are not compatible with urea because of an adduct formation that leads to poor physical quality and caking of USG briquettes. DAP, a common fertilizer for transplanted rice in tropical rice-growing countries, is compatible for preparation of USG. Agronomically, deep placement of USG is efficient in transplanted rice.

We conducted a greenhouse experiment to evaluate basal deep-placed USG containing DAP as NP fertilizer in transplanted rice. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. Soil was Vernon clay (Typic

Ustochrept, pH 8.0, CEC 33.0 cmol_c/kg), which in earlier experiments had responded to applied N and P. For a blanket basal application, 100 mg K/kg (as KC1) and 25 mg Zn/kg (as ZnSO₄) were incorporated into the soil before transplanting.

Four hills (three 3-wk-old seedlings/hill) of IR36 were transplanted (20- × 20-cm spacing) in 2-wk presubmerged and puddled soil (32 kg air-dried basis) in a wooden box (40- × 40- × 30-cm inside dimensions) with plastic lining. USG containing DAP (as tablets) was prepared by compacting a mixture of prilled urea (PU) and DAP in a 1:2 proportion. The amounts of N and P used (19.3 mg N/kg and 10.3 mg P/kg, equivalent to 40 kg N and 21 kg P/ha on area basis) were on the steep portion of their response curves for the soil used.